

The Relationship between Unemployment and Inflation Rates in Pakistan

Authors' Details:

⁽¹⁾**Muhammad Hammad Alam**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: askhammadalam@yahoo.com

⁽²⁾**Dr. Masood Hassan**

PhD, IoBM, Karachi, Pakistan and Visiting Faculty Greenwich, Karachi, Pakistan.

Email: masoodhassan1@hotmail.com (Corresponding Author)

⁽³⁾**Qasim Hamid Memon**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: qasim.memon54@gmail.com

⁽⁴⁾**Muhammad Shahzar Sani**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: shahzar.sani@gmail.com

Abstract:

This report focuses on the relationship between inflation and unemployment of Pakistan. One of the most important elements of country's security is its inflation and unemployment rate as they together, make surviving for the poor very difficult. This report mentions the 4 important factors, corruption, flawed policies, illiteracy and rapid population growth and how they all affect the rates together and what the result is of the following. The report suggests that a wider and deeper sample is to be used as the people most affected by the inflation and unemployment are the people who live in the slums and might not have the gadgets and technology to fulfill to the survey. The report highlights all the necessary factors that are to be controlled in order to maintain serenity and peace in a country. With the vast increase in the inflation rate in the following rates, the report suggests ways of controlling it and making opportunities for the locals of the country to grow financially and find work. This report records people's opinion and reactions regarding growth and should come in handy for future researchers to understand Pakistan's political instability, therefore making this research important.

Keywords: Inflation, Unemployment, Corruption, Flawed Policies, Illiteracy, Rapid Population Growth.

Introduction

Any countries two hot financial systems topics are inflation and unemployment. It is a common practice for policymakers to aim or achieving low unemployment and inflation rates. The common goal shared amongst all policy makers is to achieve a single digit rate for to ensure that the country's economy is strengthened due to strong macroeconomics. Inflation rate and unemployment rate is considered It is often a fall out with the aim of single-digit inflation and unemployment percentage about around five percent could ensure that macro-economic strength is strengthened in an economy where everything is equal. In simple words, inflation is the rate at which a countries currency's buying power decreases over a set period. Demand pull Inflation occurs when the aggregate demand of the goods and services then aggregate supply of goods and services in the economy. Cost pull inflation occur when the cost of inputs like raw material increases. Unemployment and inflation are macroeconomic variables, and it has very important effect on economic growth. Since the partition 1947, Pakistan's inflation rate stayed low or a quite a long time; it wasn't until late 2003 that Pakistan experienced an accelerated inflation. (MS Khan, 2006).

By late 2005, Pakistan's year on year inflation rate had peaked at 11% whereas the average inflation rate of that year was around 8-9% by September. Even though the inflation rate has receded since then, it is a high priority for all policy makers all around the world. A persistent and high inflation forces the policy makers to charge high tax and affects the poor a lot, the basic cost of living goes up and that corrupts the country. Riots, robbery and other illicit activities become a norm (MS Khan, 2006). According to a classical theory, called the Quantity theory of money, inflation rate is associated with high rates of money growth. It suggests, that if a government wants to replace the notes of the country, the price in terms of new rupee would be higher than before. To summarize it, the changes in the money supply executed in this way will always be associated with propionate

changes in prices having no effect on output or employment. It is believed that if the money growth doesn't affect the output, higher money growth leads to higher inflation (Agha, 2006). According to famous Friedman dictum "Inflation is always and everywhere a monetary phenomenon." However, the world is more complicated than this and monetary policy consists of more than just currency exchanges.

An interconnected issue arises that how governments get money from the system. One way is to print money to finance government deficits (Friedman, 2003). People, who are working looking for jobs but can't find it, are termed unemployable. People who work but aren't in the appropriate field are also considered unemployable. There are many factors that play a part in employment. "unemployment is an excess supply of labor resulting from a failure in the market economy", (Keynes 1936). Pakistan has a large population (estimated as 179,572,000) and stands on 6th in the ranking of most populated countries. Pakistan shares 2.56% in world population, 9th in world ranking with 75,880,000 labor force (2011). According to US central intelligence agency unemployment in Pakistan is 5.50 and stands at 57th in world ranking (2011). Pakistan has an economy growth rate of just 2.6% which is due to the political instability, growing security concern, impact of floods, high inflation and inadequate infrastructure. Pakistan stands at 113th out of 129 countries with a 7.73% youth unemployment rate, 153rd out of 230 countries with a 4.2% old age rate, 174th out of 257 countries with 60.40% 15-64 years age rate, 59th out of 257 countries with 0-14-year age rate.

Unemployment and inflation indicates the growth of the underdeveloped nations. The results state that in long run the unemployment and inflation will affect the country's growth in all the dynamics. Unemployment can be stated as a wasting the nation's manpower, it also creates welfare loss and decreases the output and results into decreased income and well-being of the citizens (Raheem, 1993).

To maintain the inflation rate there should be balance in the imports and exports to maintain the nation's treasury. Foreign and monetary policies play a very important part in this to main the spending of the government and to maximize the government earnings. The increasing inflation rate will create unemployment situations for the youth and the citizens of Pakistan. To create more employment opportunities there should be certain industries deployed to accommodate the youth. According to Jhingan (2003), unemployment can be also stated as more than two people are willing and are available for a work at a minimum wage and still they do not get any work.

This research intends to deeply investigate the causes and problems faced by the impact of increasing inflation and unemployment rate. Inflation and unemployment are the problems that have an impact on the social and economic life of every nation. The relationship of inflation and unemployment is known as the "Phillips Curve" in the economics.

This study will help us understand the current financial situation and help us analyze and figure out better plans and policies for future it will not only help us understand the relationship between the two but also help us understand the sufferers. Help policy makers in understanding how their decisions affect the working class and what psychological, financial and physical damage it causes and help people understand where the policies are to blame and where they lack working ability is to blame. Its aim is to expose underpaying jobs and how the employees are exploited in different organizations across the country. The research will show that which areas are mainly the reason behind higher inflation rate and how those results in a higher unemployment rate.

Corruption

Corruption can be defined as breaking of a rule by an elected personality or a bureaucrat for personal gain. Corruption is mostly seen in third world country, where the most common type of corruption is when a bureaucrat takes money under the table or in an offshore account where the money is not accounted. This monetary bribe is taken to bend the rules for an influential individual or for their own gain. Another most famous form of corruption is nepotism. Nepotism means an influential person, or a bureaucrat hires their own relative/person of their choice instead of hiring through an open procurement process. Nepotism is providing a known person or a family member extra favors if the person is in power in an organization (Hayaejenh, et al., 1994).

As Svensson (2005) said, we notice the same form of corruption in a nonprofit sector because while the social good is being provided, the private and social value may not coincide with it. According to Shleifer and Vishny (1993), the government officials often sell the government property for their personal gain. Moreover, Shleifer and Vishny (1993) and Svensson (2005) also say that property in this context isn't just physical as sometimes, the land is sold, but most of the times, licenses and permits are sold at a higher price.

Flawed Policies

A set of rules and laws that are set by the people in power, for the country or any organization to follow are called policies. A policy isn't harmful at all, however when the people in power make policies in order to benefit themselves are called flawed policies, and they are the ones that increase the inflation and the unemployment rates. Flawed policies come into play when the state capacities are distributed wrongfully (Khan, 2009). There isn't any correction and overseeing of the policy making bureaucrats, this creates too much discretion, and it results in flawed policies.

A policy is considered flawed when it is used by the policy maker for his, or his peers' personal gains. The government of Pakistan has tried to address some of the flaws in the policies but, because this has been going on for decades, this hasn't been possible yet. The countries that decisively opt monetary policy and not the income policies, can counter and stabilize the inflation (Debelle, 1996).

Illiteracy

There are two main ways of describing illiteracy, one is when a person can't read or write, and the other is when the person has no knowledge of a particular subject or topic. In quantitative terms, the standard of attainment in functional literacy may be equated to the skills of reading, writing, and arithmetic achieved after a set number of years of primary or elementary schooling (Paris, 1962). Pakistan's education situation is very different than the constitution of Pakistan. The country's education system is divided into five levels: primary, middle, intermediate, higher secondary certificate and university programs, graduate and undergraduate levels. The Pakistan's government launched a nationwide National Education Policy (NEP) in 1998 which operated till 2010. Its main aim was to eradicate illiteracy and to provide basic education and skillsets to all children.

The state shall provide free and compulsory education to all children of the age of 5 to 16 years old in such a manner as may be determined by law (Malik, 2011). After a lot of reforms, in 2015, Pakistan's ministry of education expects to get 100% enrollment levels amongst primary scholars. As of 2019, Pakistan's literacy rate was recorded to be around 58%, out of which less than 46.49% percent of women were illiterate and more than 69.29 percent of men being illiterate. This explains the growing unemployment in Pakistan as people don't spend time in learning a skill and they don't educate themselves either

Growing Population Rate

Pakistan's geopolitical significance has increasingly become cleared to world since 2001, and so has the country's instability. Pakistan is a country of approximately 180.1 million people (United Nations Development Program) (UNDP, 2011) Throughout the decade, Pakistan's population has suffered with a growing strife. Today Pakistan exhibits the highest rate of growth among the world's largest countries, and according to some projections will become the third most populated country in the world by the year 2050 [United Nations (1998)]. Apart from these major headlines, a bunch of people may realize that Pakistan's demographics has a huge role in Pakistan's overall security and development. With the entire economic and financial situation, Pakistan's family planning program has become stagnant. Population growth of Pakistan is on an incline curve due to lack of education and lack of family planning. On Balance, slower population growth would be beneficial to economic development for most developing countries (Kelly & Schmidt, 1994).

One of the biggest Pakistan faces is the over population. Ever since 1947, Pakistan was the 13th most populous country in the world with the total population of 32.5 million, but just 49 years later, in 1996, Pakistan's population was recorded to be a staggering 144 million people.

Corruption, Inflation and Unemployment Rate Of Pakistan

Corruption is being dishonest towards your actions in power, typically involvement of bribery, lobbying, nepotism and extortion. In 1996 Pakistan was rated as the second most corrupt nation out of 54 surveyed countries by international anti-corruption NGO Transparency International (TI). The corruption culture started from the colonial system where corrupt people were rewarded with lands and jobs as a bribery. According to the word bank international bribery exceeds US\$ 1.5 trillion yearly, which is around 2% of the world's GDP. the rate of unemployment provides the image of the country's condition and concerns the decision makers (Dope & Legan, 2018).

The causes of corruption are red-tapism, poor economic infrastructure, complex law and procedures, absence of public forum and loss of morality, honest and ethical values. Corruption effects the economic growth which includes business operations, investments and employment. Corruption slows down the economy of the country. There is a theft caused in the funds intended for the poor people or people below the poverty line. They exploit the taxpayers and creates cap between the rich and the poor. Corruption is executed mostly in cash and if it's transferred from an offshore account it is known as the black money. Political economy budget is discussed on the deficit (Alesina & Perotti, 2015)

Corruption can occur in all kinds of organization in private and in public. It disturbs the merit system and makes the process of everything expensive and difficult for the general public. According to (Gray & Kaufman, 1998; Rose-Ackerman, 1999; Bardhan, 1997; Klitgaard, 1988; Lambsdorff, 2007) it is the misuse of public power for own purposes. It has a strong effect on the economy as it reflects on the inflation.

Pakistan has a score of 28/100 on the (CPI), Corruption Perceptions Index and ranks on 140th position from the list of 180 countries in the public sector. The more the score is the country is corruption free. Corruption is only increasing day by day and is affecting the economy of the country. After plenty of study and research on the corruption and the economic reasons for it, the main purpose is to understand the link among corruption and inflation that they are not at the desired level (Piplica, 2011). The results of the study are that inflation causes corruption in various departments of an organization as the increasing prices of the goods and services are increasing at a rapid speed and while on the other hand purchasing power is constant and inflation is only increasing.

Corruption has a causal relationship with the unemployment of the country in two different angles. First, the corruption in the government departments practice to accept bribes to get job opportunities, which decreases the capability of the employee allotment. The employee is redirected, and less qualified person is given the opportunity because he/she has bribed the official in power. As bureaucrats perform their personal interest work on the nation's welfare and the money is misused for personal work. Second, mismatching the difference in the demand supply for the labor force has to face bribery by providing extra motive to the new employees to accept these practices. Is income is poorly distributed it will cause unemployment and will affect the economy (Rendahl, 2016).

Corruption also exists in the private sector, but it is on a smaller scale and within the organization, while on the other hand public sector gives more exposure and there is more power involved. As the inflation is increasing there are more job seekers who are willing to pay bribe and enter the system. If an employee pays bribe, he has entered the corrupt system and will practice the same actions when he is in the power and will also accept bribe in the future as in his/her psychological mind this is the only way how the public sector works. Government officers have the power to give a job to the person paying highest bribe (Shleifer & Vishny, 1993). In elections campaigns huge budget is spent and politicians force the workers to invest and collect money from the public which is known as corruption (Rose-Ackerman, 1999). As unemployment is increasing because of the increase in the inflation rate the minimum wage of a citizen of Pakistan has been increase by 14.4%, which means from

Rs17,370 to Rs19,870. In dollars it would be considered as \$144 currently. Corruption directly effects the inflation and the unemployment rate of the country and creates gap between the rich and the poor.

Flawed Policies, Inflation and Unemployment Rate of Pakistan

The unemployment rate and inflation fluctuate on the performance of the economy. When unemployment rate is decreasing the GDP increases which means there is increase in the industrial productions. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) calculates the value of goods that are purchased by the end user in a certain time within the country. When the GDP increases it refers those jobs will be created for the citizens and work force wages will be increased. The GDP of Pakistan is 292 USD Billion in the current times and is estimated to be 310 billion dollars in 2023 calculated on certain econometric models It is the current income and output to the Pakistan's economy. After the global crisis in 2007, the unemployment has been an issue for the researchers (Katz, 2014). Controlling the inflation and the unemployment is the goal to have a growth in the development of the country. The most important is the decision making. In this problem the richer becomes richer and poor becomes poorer. With the inflation increasing the prices of goods and services will increase while the wages stay on the same scale.

The increasing inflation will cause the economy problems such as erode purchasing power, encouraged investing and spending, and increasing the cost of borrowing. Policymakers and the citizens demand low inflation and low unemployment rate, and it is very difficult to have both as a developing country. The economy of the country works in a way that if unemployment goes down the inflation will automatically increase. And While on the other hand when inflation comes down the unemployment goes up. This is the most common problems seen in the nations worldwide. The policymakers should consider something feasible, which includes trading one objective to another. According to (Auclert, 2016), wisdom sees the distribution as an alternative effect of the policies and while on the other hand aggressive demand. In other words, more, the inflation more the opportunity cost will be high for the unemployment and decreased inflation. The economy of the country to be strong is the want to grow and stabile their industrial sector to boost their economy. Unemployment rate of the economy is a strong indicator for the currency demand equation (Arby, Malik & Hanif, 2010).

When monetary policy is implemented, it affects the aggregate demand and inflation on different kinds of channels Also, global market changes play an important role in the inflation as in current times increase in the oil prices is causing higher inflation and unemployment. Monetary policy specially targets the increasing inflation and tries to support the public. The government can accomplish a low unemployment rate which two types of policies monetary or fiscal. Monetary policy is with the central banks to increase the growth of the economy by controlling the money supply throughout the country. Excessive money is pushed into the economy in the lower interest rates and prints more notes to spur growth. Central banks take the steps to implement the policies (Blinder et al, 2017).

If unemployment rate increases from its real rate, then in result inflation rate will decrease. The unemployment rate remains constant if there is growth in the country's economy. If the rate is under the natural rate, then it leads towards that the growth is fast than highest sustainable rate, which burdens the wages and prices increase and causes inflation rate to increase. Seemly if the unemployment rate exceeds its real rate, then inflation will decrease and purchasing power would be better. Policy makers think that inflation creates more important issues than unemployment (Fisher, 2016).

Monitory policy plays an important role as it has control over the interest rates of the country's economy from deposits to lending. This effects the employment and the inflation of the country. Decision making is very important as there are political tensions going on Pakistan the foreign policy is unstable after the no confidence vote in the parliament (Fatema Iqbal, 2022). The government has been turned and new policies are being implemented which are currently causing instability in the economy with the increase rate of unemployment rate an inflation. According to (Kianmehr, 2006) unemployment rate will hold as a part of the population growing rate. In economics the research in the field has concluded in that the relationship among inflation and unemployment in the economy has been a negative relationship. Policies can be effective in boosting the

economic situation and decrease the unemployment rate to aggravate inflation. According to Yılmaz (2005), policies that increase the funding in human capital must develop as stated in endogenous growth theories.

Illiteracy, Inflation and Unemployment Rate of Pakistan

A person is literate when he has acquired the necessary knowledge and skills to participate in all activities in which literacy is required for effective functioning in his group and community, and whose achievement in reading, writing, and arithmetic allows him to continue to apply these skills to his own and the community's development. Over the last few decades, the formal availability of education for children has increased around the world. Adults can become functional illiterates despite having a successful formal education. A person who is functionally illiterate is unable to use reading, writing, and calculation skills for his or her own or the community's development.

Not only does functional illiteracy have a negative impact on personal development, but it also has a negative impact on the economy and society. In Pakistan, unemployment is another cause of illiteracy. FATA is one of the most undeveloped areas where 60% population lives in poor conditions with only 17% literacy rate (Ahmar, 2008). In Pakistan, between 5% and 6% of the population is unemployed. They have decided that literacy will not provide employment (Ali, 2010). They believed that people who learned a passion over time would be able to earn a living. Most educated people are unemployed and barely surviving in society. They are dissatisfied due to unemployment. They lose hope and are unable to guide or motivate others in the direction of education. Pakistan's unemployment is a serious problem.

It is a major hindrance to Pakistan's progress. One of the best examples of the relationship between Illiteracy and unemployment is Baluchistan. Illiteracy rate is the highest in Baluchistan which is about 45% that counts as the highest in the whole country. Moreover, it leads to unemployment and unemployment then causes illiteracy and the cycle goes on. Baluchistan's 65% population is unemployed due to illiteracy. Pakistan's educational system is severely flawed. 51% population in Pakistan is of women and most families do not allow females to study further and get employed. Incidence of the woman labor force participation is very low in Pakistan (Labour force Survey, 1999-2000).

Growing Population Rate, Inflation and Unemployment Rate of Pakistan

One of the most serious concerns facing Pakistan's unemployed is the country's uncontrolled population growth. Alexander (1997) finds a strong negative influence of inflation on growth rate of per capita GDP using a panel of OECD countries. The population of the country is currently growing at an alarmingly fast rate. Pakistan's population is growing at a rate of 2.2 percent per year, according to. Overpopulation is caused by a variety of factors, including early marriage, illiteracy, a desire for more sons, and a lack of awareness, to name a few. Because Pakistan's education system is known to be inadequate, an increase in population will inevitably result in an increase in the number of people entering the labor force who are uneducated. The government, or any other organization, will be unable to provide jobs or workplaces for the large number of illiterate people (Barro, 1995) examines the issue and finds a significant negative relationship between inflation and economic growth, considering variables like fertility rate, education, etc.

Before Covid-19, the working class in Pakistan accounted for 35 percent of the population, or 55.75 million people. This percentage has decreased to 35.04 million because of Covid-19 and other external factors, primarily due to the lockdown and shutdown of business activities in Pakistan. The unemployment rate in Pakistan was 5.7 percent in 1990s on the average which increased to 6.80 percent in 2000s on the average (Maqbool, Mahmood, Sattar, & Bhalli, 2013). After July 2020, the situation improved, as evidenced by statistical data indicating that the working class has resumed their economic activities. This brought the total to 52.56 million, or 33% of the working population. The pandemic had a negative impact on the performance of the sectors, resulting in lost income and jobs.

Transportation, manufacturing, wholesale and retail, construction, and communication were the most vulnerable sectors to the pandemic. Nearly 80% of workers have lost their jobs and are unable to find work in the

construction industry. There is a positive relationship between unemployment and population and an inverse relationship between unemployment and GDP over a period of 1986-1999 (Maqbool et al, 2013). The manufacturing sector faced the same situation, with 72 percent of labor/workers losing or unable to find work, resulting in a drop in purchasing power. After July 2020, the situation improved, as evidenced by statistical data indicating that the working class has resumed their economic activities. This amounted to 52.56 million, which has since increased to 33 million. A similar situation existed in other sectors such as transportation, retail, wholesale, and storage, with 63 percent to 67 percent of labor/workers unable to find work because of the pandemic in Pakistan (Hao, Shah, Nawaz, Nawaz, & Noman, 2020). Pakistan's total unemployment rate in 2020 will be 4.65 percent (as a percent of the total labor force).

More competition for jobs arises because of overpopulation. Not only does increased job competition make it more difficult to find work, but it also allows employers to hire employees at a lower wage because there are more applicants than jobs available. In general, an increase in the proportion of the dependent population leads to higher inflation, whereas an increase in the working-age population has the opposite effect. The elderly population, on the other hand, has an ambiguous impact. The total demand in the market rises as the population grows. Excessive demand also leads to inflation. With higher population growth, rapid urbanization, and higher per capita income in developing economies such as Pakistan, inflation has been on the rise for several years, with a few exceptions. If Pakistan's population growth has been Rs. 64366 as against Rs. 43748 at 2% since 1960, Pakistan's per capita income would have risen across the region because of rising food prices, not just in Pakistan.

Conclusion

Unemployment is one of the core problems of a developing country and the biggest problem in our society. Corruption causes hiring or recruiting the employees on an unfair process which involves bribery or favoritism. The unemployment creates a problem, and a large population migrates to the urban areas from rural areas because of lack of opportunity. Corruption exists in unemployment in every nation but in many nations, there is a lot more corruption (Orwell (1996)). As corruption is increasing the interviews are biased and pressurized by a political influence and recommendations. Corruption is one of the causes of the increase in unemployment in the nation. According to Bayart et al. (1997), a bribe is involved if any kind of transaction or favor is given in form of money, gift and land to the employer. As the corruption increases the inflation will automatically increase as the politicians in power misuse their public power and important country investments are completed in their favor of interest. The inflation and the GDP of the country is affected in this way. Corruption is the key factor in that stops the economy from growing according to Anderson and Marcouiller (2002). Pakistan is a nation which has high corruption and all anti-social steps (Noon Griffiths, (1959)).

The constant corruption is only taking Pakistan backwards and stopping its growth. It is a lot better in the private sector, but the public sector has a lot of corruption going on and initial actions should be taken to stop these kinds of crimes. The unemployment rate of the country is increasing very rapidly, this year it has increased up to 6.5 percent. The job opportunities are very less already and after the migration of people from the rural area is going to only scare the opportunities and in results the crime rate may increase. Pakistan's labor has dropped to 13 percent this year as per Kassem, Ali, and Audi. (2021). More and more foreign investment is attracted to the country to generate revenue and to create job opportunities. Stabilize the industries and growth so the foreign investors get attracted. There is a positive relationship among the investment from the foreign and domestic opportunities (Lipsey et al. (1997)). The literacy rate of Pakistan is 59.13 % currently in the year of 2022. Which means almost 40% of the population is illiterate or are working as a blue color people to earn money.

For example, as landlords get the land from their ancestors and do not take education and stay in the certain mind set. Also, while on the other hand poor class cannot afford education and their children start working at an

early age to earn bread and butter for their family the illiteracy as an effect on the unemployment and the inflation. High economic growth and decreased inflation will provide better allocation of resources and boost the employment, as rapid investments and decrease the poverty also (Gylfason, Easterly, 2011). For the guidance of economic policy designers and managers, this study recommends more empirical research. Inflation has an impact on everyone because it is regarded as a universal phenomenon.

References

- Adnan, Y., Ali, S. M., Farooqui, H. A., Kayani, H. A., Idrees, R., & Awan, M. S. (2022). High CD44 immunoexpression correlates with poor overall survival: Assessing the role of cancer stem cell markers in oral squamous cell carcinoma patients from the high-risk population of Pakistan. *International journal of surgical oncology*, 2022.
- Afzal, M. (2009). Population growth and economic development in Pakistan. *The Open Demography Journal*, 2(1).
- Agha, A. I., & Khan, M. S. (2006). An empirical analysis of fiscal imbalances and inflation in Pakistan. *SBP research Bulletin*, 2(2), 343-362.
- Ahmad, E., Arshad, M. F., & Ahmad, A. (1991). Learning and earning profiles in Pakistan's informal sector. *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 29(2), 77-98.
- Ali, S., Ali, A., & Amin, A. (2013). The impact of population growth on economic development in Pakistan. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 18(4), 483-491.
- Ashraf, M. A., & Ismat, H. I. (2016). Education and development of Pakistan: A study of current situation of education and literacy in Pakistan. *US-China Education Review B*, 6(11), 647-654.
- Ayyoub, M., Chaudhry, I. S., & Farooq, F. (2011). Does Inflation Affect Economic Growth? The case of Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences (PJSS)*, 31(1).
- Determinants of Recent Inflation in Pakistan Khan, Abdul Aleem and Ahmed, Qazi Masood and Hyder, Kalim (2007): *Determinants of Recent Inflation in Pakistan*. Published in: Working Papers/Research Report 66 (March 2007)
- Does corruption impede innovation in developing economies? Insights from Pakistan: *a call for policies reforms*. *Crime, Law and Social Change*, 75(2), 93-117. M. (2001).
- Economic analysis of corruption: evidence - Afshan Uroos, Malik Shahzad Shabbir, Muhammad Umar Zahid, Ghulam Yahya & Bilal Ahmed Abbas hakeel, Muhammad & Ahmed, Aziz & Sharif, Shahbaz. (2020). Linkages of Corruption with Income, *Inflation, and Income Inequality in Pakistan*. Federal Reserve Bank of *St. Louis Review*, May/June 2009, 91(3), pp. 107-26
- Hardee, K., & Leahy, E. (2008). Population, fertility and family planning in Pakistan: a program in stagnation. *Population Action International*, 3(3), 1-12.
- Harman, D. (1970). *Illiteracy: An Overview*.
- International Labor organization, 2001. Islamabad, Pakistan: Federal Bureau of Statistics. Jarque, C.M. and A.K. Bera, 1987. *A test for normality of observations and regression residuals*. *International Statistical Review*, 55(2): 163-172
- Jamshid, R., Iqbal, A., Siddiqui, M. (2010). Cointegration-Causality Analysis between Public Expenditures and Economic Growth in Pakistan. *European Journal Social Sciences*, vol.13 (no.4). *Journal of Economic Surveys* (2019) Vol. 33, No. 4, pp. 1199–1231
- Kerse, G., & Babadağ, M. (2018). I'm out if nepotism is in: The relationship between nepotism, job standardization and turnover intention. *Ege Academic Review*, 18(4), 631-644.

- Keynes, J.M., 1936. The general theory of employment, interest and money. New York: Macmillan Cambridge University Press.
- Khan, A., Jadoon, M. A., Alam, I., & Jawad, M. (2015). Illiteracy: A Threat to Peace in Federally Administrated Tribal Areas (FATA) of Pakistan. *Peshawar Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Sciences (PJPBS)*, 1(1), 61-71.
- Khan, M. S., & Schimmelpfennig, A. (2006). Inflation in Pakistan. *The Pakistan development review*, 185-202.
- Khan, M. S., & Schimmelpfennig, A. (2006). Inflation in Pakistan. *The Pakistan development review*, 185-202.
- Malik, A. B. (2011). *Policy analysis of education in Punjab Province*. Islamabad, Pakistan: UNESCO. Retrieved January 4, 2017
- Malik, G. and Chowdhury, A. (2001). Inflation and Economic Growth: Evidence from Four South Asian Countries, *Asia-Pacific Development Journal*, 8 (1), 123-135.
- Maqbool, M. S., Mahmood, T., Sattar, A., & Bhalli, M. N. (2013). Determinants of unemployment: Empirical evidences from Pakistan. *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 191-208.
- Memon, G. R. (2007). Education in Pakistan: The key issues, problems, and the new challenges. *Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 47-55.
- Mohamad Kassem, Amjad Ali, & Marc Audi. (2021). Unemployment Rate, Population Density and Crime Rate in Punjab (Pakistan): An Empirical Analysis. *Bulletin of Business and Economics (BBE)*, 8(2), 92-104.
- Mubarik, Y. A., & Riazuddin, R. (2005). *Inflation and growth: An estimate of the threshold level of inflation in Pakistan*. Karachi: State Bank of Pakistan.
- Musgrave, A. (1981). 'UNREAL ASSUMPTIONS' IN ECONOMIC THEORY: THE F-TWIST UNTWISTED. *Kyklos*, 34(3), 377-387.
- Naqvi, Z. F., Shahnaz, L., & Arif, G. M. (2002). How do women decide to work in Pakistan? *The Pakistan development review*, 495-513.
- Nelson, E. (2004). Monetary policy neglect and the great inflation in Canada, Australia, and New Zealand. *FRB of St. Louis Working Paper No.*
- Qayyum, A. (2006). Money, inflation, and growth in Pakistan. *The Pakistan development review*, 203-212.
- Samimi, A. J., Abedini, M., & Abdollahi, M. (2012). Corruption and inflation tax in selected developing countries. *Middle East Journal of Scientific Research*, 11(3), 391-395.
- Schoeman, C., D. Blaauw and A. Pretorius (2008), An investigation into the determinants of the South African unemployment rate 1970-2002. *Acta Academica*, 40(3), 67-84
- Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1997). A survey of corporate governance. *The journal of finance*, 52(2), 737-783.
- Siddiqui, F. A., & Mahmood, N. (1998). Population Growth and Development Prospects for Pakistan [with Comments]. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 557-574.
- Solomon, M. and Wet, A. (2004). The Effect of a Budget Deficit on Inflation: *The Case of Pakistan*. SAJEMS NS, vol.7 (no.1).
- Svensson, J. (2005). Eight questions about corruption. *Journal of economic perspectives*, 19(3), 19-42.
- The Impact of Inflation and Unemployment on Subjective Personal and Country Evaluations United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2011). *UNDP Pakistan Annual Report 2011*. Retrieved January 4, 2017
- Volume: 1 Issue: 1 08-Jun-2013, *World Applied Sciences Journal*, Vol. 14, No. 7, pp.

Zafar, Z. and Zahid, M. (1998). Macroeconomic determinant of economic growth in Pakistan. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 37, 127-148.

Zaidi, S.A (2005). *The Issues in Pakistan Economy*. Oxford University Press, Karachi.